

Bis (Iodomethyl) Mercury as a CH₂ Transfer Reagent**

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Bis (iodomethyl) mercury, Hg(CH₂I)₂, is an effective transfer agent of one CH₂ group to olefins to form cyclopropanes. Transfer of the second group (i.e., from ICH₂-HgI) is not a favourable process. However, the ICH₂HgI/Ph₂Hg or the ICH₂HgI/(PhCH₂)₂Hg couples serve to transfer the second CH₂ group to olefins.

IN previous research we had shown *bis (bromomethyl) mercury, Hg(CH₂Br)₂*, to be a reasonably effective CH₂ transfer agent to olefins to give cyclopropanes¹. Bromomethylmercuric bromide and iodomethylmercuric iodide reacted similarly in the presence of stoichiometric amounts of diphenylmercury. A direct CH₂ transfer from the mercurial (rather than a free CH₂ mechanism) was suggested¹. Although the yields of cyclopropanes obtained with the more nucleophilic olefins were fairly good, these reagents were not suitable for larger-scale synthetic application. *Bis (bromomethyl) mercury and bromomethylmercuric bromide* were prepared by the reaction of mercuric bromide with diazomethane², a reagent which is both toxic and hazardous. Iodomethyl mercuric iodide was prepared by the direct reaction of diiodomethane with elemental mercury and its purification was difficult³. Neither of these reactions was suitable for rapid accumulation of larger amounts of these mercurials.

It was the development of an improved route to Hg(CH₂I)₂ (eq. 1)⁴ which led us to reexamine the application of this reagent, alone and in combination with a diorganomercurial, as a CH₂ transfer agent to olefins.

Experimental

Preparation of bis(iodomethyl)mercury⁴: A flame-dried one-liter three-necked, round-bottomed flask equipped with a magnetic stirring assembly, a reflux condenser topped with a nitrogen inlet tube and a pressure-equalizing addition funnel was charged with 300 ml of 1.73 M EtZnI (0.52 mol; prepared by reaction of zinc-copper couple and iodoethane) in THF. To this solution was added dropwise with stirring 152 g (0.54 mol) of diiodomethane. An exothermic reaction resulted. When the mixture had cooled to room temperature, a solution of 68 g (0.25 mol) of mercuric chloride in 150 ml of dry THF was added dropwise with stirring. The reaction

mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight, during which time a white precipitate formed. Filtration provided 90 g (0.187 mol, 75%) of Hg(CH₂I)₂, m.p. 77-79° (lit.⁴ m.p. 79-81°). The product was washed several times with anhydrous diethyl ether, dried and stored in the refrigerator. Recrystallization of a small portion from chloroform did not result in a higher melting point. Further crops of the product, obtained from the mother liquor, were rather impure.

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury with mercuric iodide: Mercuric iodide, 1.0 g (2.2 mmol) and 1.2 g (2.4 mmol) of bis(iodomethyl)mercury were intimately mixed and heated on a steam bath until molten. After 30 min of heating, most of the red colour had been discharged. TLC indicated only a small spot indicative of bis(iodomethyl)mercury and a spot with R_f equivalent to that for authentic⁵ iodomethylmercuric iodide.

When the same reagents were mixed and stirred in benzene at room temperature, the dispersed colour of mercuric iodide was discharged in a few minutes; an oily solid which gradually turned yellow precipitated during this time. TLC again indicated that the bis(iodomethyl)mercury had been consumed and iodomethylmercuric iodide had been formed.

Reactions of bis(iodomethyl)mercury with olefins: The reactions were carried out in flamed-out, three-necked, round bottomed flasks of appropriate size (usually 25 or 50 ml) which were equipped with a thermometer, a reflux condenser, rubber septum for sample removal by syringe, a nitrogen inlet tube and a magnetic stir-bar. All reactions were carried out under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen or argon. The flask was charged with the mercurial, the olefin and, if any was used, the solvent, in the indicated quantities (Table 1) and the resulting mixture was stirred and heated for the indicated time. Aliquots (0.1-0.2 ml) were withdrawn by syringe without opening the system to air when possible. In the latter stages of several reactions, clogging of the

** Dedicated, with best wishes, to Professor R. C. Mehrotra on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

syringe made this procedure impossible; in these cases, a disposable pipet was used. Product yields were determined by quantitative gas chromatography using appropriate internal standards. Samples were isolated by glc and their nmr and/or ir spectra were compared with those of authentic samples. Details are given in the M.I.T. Ph.D. theses of C.K.H. and D.D.

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury with cyclooctene: Bis(iodomethyl)mercury, 4.0 g (8.3 mmol), 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane and 20 ml (154 mmol) of cyclooctene were heated to 85° for 26 hr. The red colour of mercuric iodide appeared in the reaction mixture after the first 6 hr of heating. After cooling, filtration yielded 3.45 g of a mixture of red and yellow solid with no defined melting point. The yield of bicyclo[6.1.0]nonane observed based on the transfer of one methylene group is listed below:

Time	Yield
1 hr	43%
2 hr	78%
6 hr	98%
26 hr	125%

Similar descriptions of the experiments listed in Table 1 are given in the Ph.D. thesis of D.D.

New cyclopropanes prepared in this study:

cis-1-tert-butyl-2-methylcyclopropane, n^{25}_D 1.4128, obtained as the sole product in the reaction of $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ with *cis*- $\text{Me}_3\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3$. Anal. Found: C, 85.62; H, 14.37. Calcd. for C_8H_{16} ; C, 85.63; H, 14.37%. ^1H NMR (CCl_4): δ -0.20-0.70 (m, 4H, cyclopropane H), 0.95 (s, 9H, Me_3C) and 1.17 ppm (d, 3H, CHCH_3).

trans-1-tert-butyl-3-methylcyclopropane, n^{25}_D 1.3982, obtained as the sole product in the reaction of $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ with *trans*- $\text{Me}_3\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3$. Anal. Found: C, 85.49; H, 14.38. Calcd. for C_8H_{16} ; C, 85.63; H, 14.37%. ^1H NMR (CCl_4): δ -0.20-0.50 (m, 4H, cyclopropane H), 0.80 (s, 9H, Me_3C) and 1.00 (d, 3H, CHCH_3).

In both cases a stereospecific reaction was observed. Although the stereochemistry of the products is not proven by experiment, it is reasonable to assume that the relative $\text{Me}_3\text{C}/\text{CH}_3$ geometry was retained on going from the olefin to the cyclopropane.

Reaction of iodomethylmercuric iodide and diphenylmercury with cyclooctene: Iodomethylmercuric iodide, 4.7 g (10 mmol), 3.55 g (10 mmol) of diphenylmercury, 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane and 20 ml of cyclooctene were heated to 85° for 30 hr. Filtration of the cooled reaction mixture afforded 6.92 g (85%) of phenylmercuric iodide, m.p. 240° (lit.⁹ m.p. 266°). The yield of product observed is given below:

Time	Yield
1 hr	7%
3 hr	28%
6 hr	42%
12 hr	59%
23 hr	76%
29.5 hr	78%

Reactions of bis(iodomethyl)mercury, mercuric iodide and diphenylmercury with cyclooctene: Bis(iodomethyl)mercury, 2.4 g (5.0 mmol), 2.3 g (5.0 mmol) of mercuric iodide, 3.55 g (10 mmol) of diphenylmercury, 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane and 20 ml of cyclooctene were heated to 85° for 34 hr; the mercuric iodide and bis(iodomethyl)mercury were not pre-mixed. The cooled reaction mixture gave 7.92 g (97%) of phenylmercuric iodide, m.p. 257°. The yield of product observed at each time interval is shown below:

Time	Yield
1 hr	11%
3 hr	39%
6 hr	57%
12 hr	78%
23 hr	88%
29.5 hr	93%
34 hr	93%

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury and dibenzylmercury with cyclooctene: Bis(iodomethyl)mercury, 2.4 g (5.0 mmol), 1.9 g (5.0 mmol, Alfa) of dibenzylmercury, 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane and 22 ml (170 mmol) of cyclooctene were heated for 21 hr; after 5 min at 85°, the mixture had become homogeneous. The cooled reaction mixture gave 3.2 g (76%) of benzylmercuric iodide, m.p. 104° (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 107°) upon filtration. The yield of product observed is given below:

Time	Yield
1 hr	12%
2.5 hr	31%
4 hr	48%
7 hr	75%
17.5 hr	91%
21 hr	90%

Reaction of iodomethylmercuric iodide and dibenzylmercury with cyclooctene: Iodomethylmercuric iodide, 4.7 g (10 mmol), 3.8 g (10 mmol, Alfa) of dibenzylmercury, 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane and 20 ml (154 mmol) of cyclooctene were heated for 26 hr; after 5 min of heating to 85° all of the reagents had dissolved. Filtration of the cooled mixture yielded 6.8 g (80%) of benzylmercuric iodide, m.p. 109-112°. The yield of product observed is given below:

Time	Yield
1 hr	30%
2 hr	60%
4 hr	69%
6 hr	75%
26 hr	75%

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury, mercuric iodide and dibenzylmercury with cyclooctene: Bis(iodomethyl)mercury, 1.57 g (3.25 mmol) and 1.47 g (3.25

mmol) of mercuric iodide were stirred in 10 ml of cyclooctene for 15 min at *ca* 50° during which time most of the red colour was discharged and a small amount of an oily orange precipitate was formed. To this was added 2.50 g (6.5 mmol) of dibenzylmercury, 1.00 ml (4.74 mmol) of undecane and 10 ml of cyclooctene and the reaction mixture was heated at 85° for 12 hr. All of the reagents had dissolved after heating for 5 min. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered to give 3.8 g (70%) of benzylmercuric iodide, m.p. 110°. The yield is given below :

Time	Yield
1 hr	37%
2 hr	55%
3 hr	62%
4 hr	67%
5.5 hr	68%
8 hr	71%
11 hr	71%

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury, mercuric iodide and dicyclohexylmercury with cyclooctene : Bis(iodomethyl)mercury, 2.41 g (5.00 mmol) and 2.27 g (5.00 mmol) of mercuric iodide were heated to *ca* 50° in 10 ml of cyclooctene for 15 min. Dicyclohexylmercury, 3.70 g (10 mmol), 10 ml of cyclooctene and 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane were added and the mixture was heated to 85° for 8 hr. The cooled mixture was filtered to give 7.8 g (92%) of crude cyclohexylmercuric iodide, m.p. 130° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 142-144°). The yield is given below :

Time	Yield
1 hr	11%
2 hr	26%
3 hr	44%
5.5 hr	58%
7.5 hr	58%

A similar reaction from which no aliquots were withdrawn did not show an increase in yield.

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury, mercuric iodide, and bis(phenyldimethylsilylmethyl)mercury with cyclooctene : Bis(iodomethyl)mercury, 2.41 g (5.0 mmol) and 2.27 g (5.0 mmol) of mercuric iodide were heated in 10 ml of cyclooctene until the red colour had been discharged. To this were added 5.0 g (10 mmol) of bis(phenyldimethylsilylmethyl)mercury¹², 1.00 ml (4.75 mmol) of undecane and 5 ml of cyclooctene; the mixture was heated at 85° for 48 hr. The yield is given below :

Time	Yield
3 hr	12%
7 hr	41%
19 hr	64%
22 hr	73%
25 hr	76%
34 hr	80%
48 hr	81%

Results and Discussion

Reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury alone with olefins. When bis(iodomethyl)mercury was heated with cyclooctene in the absence of solvent at 80°, transfer of one CH₂ group per mole of reagent was complete within 6 hr (eq. 2). Transfer of the

second CH₂ group occurred much more slowly under these conditions when simple magnetic stirring was used. In view of this promising result, we examined Hg(CH₂I)₂/olefin reactions in greater detail.

The progress of the CH₂ transfer process can be followed visually since the second step (eq. 3) forms red mercuric iodide. In practise, the reaction flask

was charged with 5 mmol of Hg(CH₂I)₂ and, usually, 10 ml of the olefin which also served as the solvent. As this mixture was heated and stirred, the mercurial partly dissolved, but usually the major portion remained at the bottom of the flask as an immiscible oil. The latter ranged in appearance from colourless to yellow to pale green in the various reactions. As the reaction progressed, the oil gradually became more viscous and finally solidified to a white or yellow solid. On continued heating, the solid phase acquired a reddish colouration which intensified until all or most of the solid present was deep red. The rate at which these changes occurred could be broadly correlated, in a qualitative sense, with the reactivity of the olefin used. The changes occurred in relatively quick succession with reactive olefins, but very slowly with poorly reactive ones. The progress of cyclopropane product formation usually was monitored by means of quantitative gas-liquid chromatography (glc), and the reactions were stopped when no further growth of the product peak was observed, or when the solid phase in the flask was deep red. In view of the difficulties in effecting rapid and complete utilization of ICH₂HgI in the second step, we report product yields in terms of eq. 2=100%. Thus if some utilization of ICH₂HgI occurs, yields greater than 100% will be obtained. The results of our experiments are presented in Table 1.

Examination of Table 1 shows that the temperature at which the reaction is carried out is an important rate-determining factor. Thus, at 83° the reaction of Hg(CH₂I)₂ with cyclooctene gave bicyclo [6.1.0] nonane in 156% yield in a 100 hr reaction period. In contrast, at 112° the reaction was much faster, giving the cyclopropane product in 120% yield within 2 hr. A further temperature increase to 138° gave a 125% product yield in less than an hour. Such behaviour, however, was not found with the less reactive olefins. For instance, Hg(CH₂I)₂ reacted with *trans*-4,4-dimethyl-2-pentene at 77° to give the expected cyclopropane in 43% yield after 7 days. When the same olefin was allowed to react with this mercurial in a sealed tube at 110°, a reaction time of 8 days gave only a 44% product yield.

TABLE I - REACTIONS OF bis(IODOMETHYL)MERCURY WITH OLEFINS

Olefin ^a (ml)	Reaction Temperature	Reaction Time (days) ^c	Product (% Yield) ^d	Mercurial byproduct (% yield) ^e
	(6) ^b	25°	(trace)	-
	(6) ^b	80°	(148)	HgI ₂ (j)
	(18) ^g	83 ± 2°	(156)	HgI ₂ (53)
	(12)	112 ± 2°	(120)	HgI ₂ (87)
	(12)	138°	(125)	HgI ₂ (84)
n-C ₅ H ₁₁ CH=CH ₂ (12)	94°	10	(62)	HgI ₂ (78)
(76)	HgI ₂ (16)			
(70)	HgI ₂ (38)			
AcOCH=CH ₂ (10)	72°	20	(107)	ICH ₂ HgI (86)
PhCH=CH ₂ (4) ^f	80°	4	(118)	HgI ₂ (68)
Me ₃ SiCH=CH ₂ (10)	55°	35	(30)	Hg(CH ₂ I) ₂ (63)
(46) ^h	1			
Me ₂ C=CHMe (10)	73°	4.0	(102)	HgI ₂ (96)
(102)	HgI ₂ (83)			
(70) ^h	1			
(44) ^h	1			

a. Unless otherwise noted, excess olefin was used as solvent and 5 mmol of Hg(CH₂I)₂ were used.

b. In 12 ml of benzene; 8.5 mmol of Hg(CH₂I)₂.

c. Reaction time stated is that necessary for obtaining the stated yield of cyclopropane. Actual reaction times were often much longer and were required to obtain the stated yield of mercurial byproduct, e. g. HgI₂.

d. Percentage yield is based on the amount of starting mercurial and on the transfer of one methylene (eq. 2).

e. In 10.5 ml benzene; olefin/mercurial ratio = 3.

f. In 5 ml benzene; olefin/mercurial ratio = 7.

g. 8.08 mmol of Hg(CH₂I)₂.

h. Not necessarily the maximum yield obtainable; reaction stopped at this point arbitrarily.

i. Not identified.

j. Not determined.

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The rate of product formation appears to depend also on the initial olefin concentration. Reactions proceeded fastest when no solvent was used and rates decreased as benzene diluent was added. However, there was no substantial effect on the

final yield of cyclopropane product as solvent was added. In some cases a diluent was necessary. Thus, reaction of Hg(CH₂I)₂ with neat styrene at 80° resulted in extensive polymerization of the reactive olefin. In the presence of benzene diluent at 80°

 TABLE 2 - COMPARATIVE REACTIONS OF Hg(CH₂Br)₂ AND Hg(CH₂I)₂ WITH OLEFINS^h

Reaction ^a	X = Br ^{b,c}		X = I ^d	
	Cyclopropane yield (%)	Reaction time (days)	Cyclopropane yield (%)	Reaction time (days)
	82	4.0	148	3.0
	65 ^e	8 hr	125	< 1 hr
	62	20 hr	{ 60 70	{ 5 hrs 52 hrs
	74	8	{ 65 76	{ 8 17
	46 ^f	5.75	{ 52 ^g 62 ^g	{ 5 10
	25	34 days	100	15 days
	22	8 days	118	4 days
	36	23 days	107	20 days
	~6	20 days	~6	25 days

- Reaction conditions denoted in this column apply to X=Br and to X=I.
- Data from reference 14.
- Unless otherwise stated here or in the "Reaction" column, all reactions were carried out in benzene at 80-85°.
- Unless otherwise stated, all reactions were conducted in neat olefin at its reflux temperature.
- Solvent was chlorobenzene.
- Solvent was benzene/ethylbenzene, 5 : 1 by volume.
- Olefin b.p. 94°.
- Cyclopropane yields are based on transfer of one XCH₂ group; yields over 100% signify additional transfer of second XCH₂ group.

some polymerization of styrene did take place, but a reasonable yield of cyclopropylbenzene nevertheless was obtained.

The structure and the nature of the olefin also have a profound effect on the reactivity of olefins toward $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$. As expected, nucleophilic olefins such as cyclooctene and tetramethylethylene underwent relatively rapid reactions to give good yields of cyclopropane product. Monosubstituted olefins such as 1-heptene and 3,3-dimethyl-1-pentene were considerably less reactive. As expected, a *cis*-1,2-dialkylethylene, *cis*- $\text{Me}_3\text{CCH}=\text{CHCH}_3$, was more reactive than the *trans* isomer and the reactions in each case were stereospecific.

It would be of interest to compare the reactivities of $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{Br})_2$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ as CH_2 transfer reagents. This is not possible because different reaction conditions were used in the studies of the respective $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{X})_2$ /olefin reactions. Nevertheless, a comparison is possible in terms of the synthetic utility of the two reagents.

The improvements of $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ over the bromomethyl-analog, as well as the unfavourable similarities, are shown in Table 2. It is clear that $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ is a more useful reagent than $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{Br})_2$. However, there are severe limitations on the utility of $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ and it cannot compete with the Simmons-Smith reagent, ICH_2ZnI , especially after the latter has been improved considerably⁶.

There remains an unexplained discrepancy between the extent of second step CH_2 transfer (i.e., eq. 3) and the yield of HgI_2 in a number of the reactions in Table 1. In analogy to the known mode of thermal decomposition of $\text{PhHgCCl}_2\text{Br}$ ⁶, when the olefin is unreactive and/or the reaction temperature is high, CH_2 transfer into the $\text{Hg}-\text{C}$ bond of the reagent(s) present may become competitive as suggested in eq. 4.

This suggestion is speculation and has not been tested. Our ideas about the nature of the CH_2 transfer process from *bis*(halomethyl)mercury compounds to olefins also are largely speculative and have been presented in sufficient detail in our paper of the $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{Br})_2$ /olefin reactions¹. We remain certain that free CH_2 is not involved.

Reaction of iodomethylmercuric iodide/diorganomercurial and bis(iodomethyl)mercury/diorganomercurial systems with olefins. As mentioned above, iodomethylmercuric iodide can serve as a useful source of CH_2 when it is heated with an olefin in the presence of a stoichiometric quantity of diphe-

nylmercury¹. Redistribution processes to give PhHgCH_2I and $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ (eq. 5 and 6) occur

in this system, and it was thought possible that PhHgCH_2I also is a CH_2 transfer reagent. In analogy to the known⁷ PhHgCH_2Cl , this compound probably is quite unstable with respect to disproportionation as shown in eq. 6, and it was never isolated during the course of those studies.

Our new synthesis of *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury by the organozinc route allowed us to examine in more detail the synthetic utility of iodomethylmercuric iodide as a CH_2 transfer agent to olefins. The reaction of *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury with mercuric iodide, with or without added solvent, on the steam bath provides a facile synthesis of ICH_2HgI . The conversion can be followed by noting the disappearance of the red colour of mercuric iodide. However, the prior synthesis of ICH_2HgI is not necessary; it can be prepared *in situ* by heating equimolar quantities of $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_2\text{I})_2$ and HgI_2 to 50° in the presence of the olefin which is to be cyclopropanated.

A comparison of the rate of bicyclo [6.1.0] nonane formation when cyclooctene and diphenylmercury are heated with authentic iodomethylmercuric iodide and with a mixture of mercuric iodide and *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the reaction follows the same profile in both cases. The addition of diphenylmercury has provided a means of utilizing

Fig. 1

both methylene units within 30 hr of heating. Thus, in the Hg(CH₂I)₂/HgI₂/Ph₂Hg system we have an effective reagent for the preparation of cyclopropanes from olefins. An extensive study of the reactivities of various olefins toward this three-mercurial reagent was not carried out, but we assume that they will parallel those found for the first ICH₂ group of Hg(CH₂I)₂ alone since the same basic mechanism must be involved.

At the time we were reexamining the ICH₂HgI/Ph₂Hg reagent, Scheffold and Michel⁸ reported that CH₂ transfer from benzyl(iodomethyl)mercury to olefins was a more facile process than our earlier described¹ (BrCH₂)₂Hg/Ph₂Hg- or ICH₂HgI/Ph₂Hg-olefin reactions. However, PhCH₂HgCH₂I was prepared by the reaction of PhCH₂HgI with diazomethane, which, as we have pointed out in the introduction, is a toxic and potentially hazardous reagent. Accordingly, we carried out a brief study to see if an equimolar mixture of *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury and dibenzylmercury is equally effective as a CH₂ transfer reagent as PhCH₂HgCH₂I.

When *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury was heated with dibenzylmercury in cyclooctene at 85°, transfer of both CH₂ groups was complete within 17 hr. To determine if dibenzylmercury was undergoing redistribution with (ICH₂)₂Hg (eq. 7), or with ICH₂HgI formed from the loss of CH₂ from the former reagent (eq. 8), dibenzylmercury was heated with

authentic iodomethylmercuric iodide in cyclooctene. Using this reagent system, transfer of CH₂ was complete within 6 hr. Thus, dibenzylmercury interacts principally with ICH₂HgI. The same results are obtained when ICH₂HgI is prepared *in situ*.

A consideration of the data from these benzyl systems indicates that, in at least this case, RHg-CH₂I is itself serving as a source of methylene and not merely serving as a route to *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury.

If the alkylmercurial was not itself undergoing α-elimination, then the rate of formation of bicyclo [6.1.0] nonane could not be faster in the reaction of ICH₂HgI with dibenzylmercury than for the reaction of (ICH₂)₂Hg and dibenzylmercury.

When iodomethylmercuric iodide and dicyclohexylmercury were heated in cyclooctene, an increase in rate of methylene transfer was observed in comparison to that for the diphenylmercury system. However, the yield of the product observed was only 58%—an increase of only 16% over what could be obtained in the same time by using *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury alone.

Heating *bis*(phenyldimethylsilylmethyl)mercury with iodomethylmercuric iodide in cyclooctene again resulted in transfer of CH₂. In this case, however, the rate of transfer was no greater than that for the phenyl-based systems. Thus, the observed rate of methylene transfer is dependent on the particular alkyl group used.

This brief investigation has demonstrated that *bis*(iodomethyl)mercury is the reagent of choice when an organomercury source of CH₂ is desired. It can be used directly; one methylene is transferred quickly with the reactive olefin, cyclooctene. If the use of both methylene groups is desired, then conversion of Hg(CH₂I)₂ to ICH₂HgI with mercuric iodide and redistribution of ICH₂HgI with dibenzylmercury provide a relatively reactive reagent. All of these mercurials—ICH₂HgI, Hg(CH₂I)₂, (PhCH₂)₂Hg and Ph₂Hg—which provide the basis for these various CH₂ transfer systems, are crystalline solids which are stable on prolonged storage. Larger quantities can be accumulated and will be ready for use when needed. Although this point was not investigated, the reactive PhCH₂HgCH₂I of Scheffold and Michel should be obtainable by the reaction of ICH₂HgI with benzylmagnesium halide or benzylzinc halide.

Appendix

The reaction of bis(iodomethyl)mercury with elemental mercury.

The "insertion" of elemental mercury (usually a light-induced, free radical process) into C-I bonds of iodoalkanes and diiodomethane is a well-known reaction which dates back to the 1850s for the first examples¹³. The light-induced reaction of elemental mercury with diiodomethane gave both ICH₂HgI and IHgCH₂HgI¹⁴. The second product may have been formed by the reaction of the first with mercury, but it also is a product of the thermal decomposition of ICH₂HgI¹⁵. In view of this known chemistry, it was anticipated that the reaction of Hg(CH₂I)₂ might provide a route to the novel trimercurial IHgCH₂HgCH₂HgI. Such we found to be the case.

A mixture of 2.41 g (5.0 mmol) of Hg(CH₂I)₂, 2.11 g (10.6 mmol) of mercury and 15 ml of benzene was stirred at reflux under nitrogen with normal laboratory illumination for 15 hr. During the course of this time a heavy white powder was formed. TLC examination of the colourless supernatant solution showed the presence of only a trace of the starting mercurial and no other soluble products. The reaction mixture was decanted from the small amount of mercury which remained and the benzene suspension of the white product thus obtained was filtered to afford 4.40 g of IHgCH₂HgCH₂HgI, m.p. 196-198°. The product was washed with benzene and dried at 110°. Anal. Found: C, 2.74; H, 0.59; I, 29.32. Calcd. for C₂H₄I₂Hg₃: C, 2.72; H, 0.46; I, 28.72%. ¹H NMR (dmso-d₆): δ 3.30 (s). IR (KBr pellet): 2898w, 1327broad, 959m, 633m, 600s, 560sh and 502m (cm⁻¹).

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